

Acute oral toxicity of supramolecular complex of ivermectin

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Annotation

Research objective: to study the acute oral toxicity of the supramolecular complex of ivermectin.

Materials and Methods. The object of the study were laboratory animals kept in the vivarium of VNI-IP. Preclinical study of supramolecular complex of ivermectin was carried out in accordance with the "Guidelines for experimental (preclinical) study of new pharmacological substances". The Litchfield and Wilcoxon method modified by Z. Roth was used to process experimental data for the study of the supramolecular complex of ivermectin. Acute oral toxicity was studied by gastric administration of ivermectin complex and ivermectin substance for control in increased doses to white mice and rats with live weight of 18 and 160-180 g, respectively. For each dose, 10 mice and 6 rats were taken. The drug was administered once with a gastric tube in doses ranging from 40 to 350 mg/kg DV. The general condition and behavior of the animals, possible death, and manifestation of intoxication symptoms were monitored for 14 days.

Results and Discussion. The picture of intoxication in mice and rats was comparable; the dependence of the number of dead individuals on the administered dose was also revealed. The toxicity of the supramolecular complex of ivermectin was 3 times lower than that of the ivermectin substance. Introduction of arabinogalactan into the composition of the preparation contributes to leveling of the negative effect of DV (ivermectin) in the supramolecular complex preparation on the organism of animals. The LD50 of ivermectin substance for mice amounted to 82.0, for rats - 165.0 mg/kg, supramolecular complex of ivermectin - 280.0 and 298.0 mg/kg (according to the preparation 14500 and 14598 mg/kg), respectively. According to GOST 12.1.007-76 supramolecular complex of ivermectin belongs to the 4th class of hazard.

Keywords: acute toxicity, supramolecular complex, ivermectin, mice, rats, lethal dose.

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Acute Oral Toxicity of the Supramolecular Complex of Ivermectin

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Abstract

The purpose of the research is to study the acute oral toxicity of the supramolecular complex of ivermectin.

Materials and methods. The object of the study was laboratory animals kept in the vivarium of the All-Russian Scientific Research Institute of Fundamental and Applied Parasitology of Animals and Plants. The preclinical study of the ivermectin complex was carried out in accordance with "Guidelines for the Experimental (Preclinical) Study of New Pharmacological Substances". To process the experimental data in the study of the supramolecular complex of ivermectin, the method proposed by Litchfield and Wilcoxon modified by Z. Roth was used. Acute oral toxicity was carried out with the administration of a complex of ivermectin and the substance ivermectin into the stomach for control in high doses in white mice and rats with a live weight of 18 and 160-180 g respectively. For each dose, 10 mice and 6 rats were used. The drug was administered once using a gastric tube in a doses from 40 to 350 mg/kg in terms of AS. For 14 days the general condition and behavior of animals, possible death, as well as well as the manifestation of symptoms of intoxication has been monitored.

Results and discussion. As our studies showed, the picture of intoxication in both species (mice and rats) was comparable, and the dependence of the number of dead animals on the administered dose was also revealed. Unlike the substance ivermectin, the toxicity of the supramolecular complex is 3 times lower. The introduction of arabinogalactan into the composition of the drug helps to level the negative effect of AS (ivermectin) in the supramolecular complex preparation on the animal organism. LD50 of ivermectin substance for mice was 82.0, for rats - 165.0 mg/kg, supramolecular complex of ivermectin - 280.0 and 298.0 mg/kg respectively (according to the drug 14500 and 14598 mg/kg). According to GOST 12.1.007-76, the supramolecular complex of ivermectin belongs to hazard class 4.

Keywords: acute toxicity, antiparasitic supramolecular complex of ivermectin, mouse, rat, lethal dose (LD).

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Introduction

The beginning of toxicity studies was laid by Paracelsus (1493-1541), who identified the chemical substances that cause toxicity in animals and plants; determined the harmless and beneficial properties of toxins and proved the dose-response relationship for drugs. He is credited with the statement: "All substances are poisons; there are none that are not poisons; the correct dose distinguishes a poison from a cure".

Mathieu Orfila (1787-1853) was a Spanish physician, chemist, and toxicologist; he determined the relationship between poisons and their biological properties, and demonstrated specific organ damage caused by toxins; modern toxicology begins with him.

The use of animals in preclinical toxicity studies began in 1920 when J. W. Trevan proposed the use of the 50% lethal dose test (LD₅₀) to determine the lethal dose of certain chemicals. In the early 1960s, thousands of babies were born with birth defects caused by thalidomide. After that, they began to study the toxicity of all pharmaceutical substances of investigational and new drugs.

Toxicologic drug screening methods and toxicology studies

of individual substances were developed in the mid-1900s.

Preclinical toxicological studies are aimed at detecting the activity of toxic substances arising from the introduction of a pharmacological substance into the body of laboratory animals. They are an integral part of studies proving the safety of medicines. Preclinical toxicological studies are necessary to determine the possible risk of animal death during clinical trials of medicinal products.

The work was carried out under State Assignment 0577-2014-0006: Creation of new generation antiparasitic drugs based on supramolecular nanoscale delivery systems, study of metabolism, biotransformation, pharmacokinetics in the animal body, pharmaco-toxicological properties and efficacy of therapeutic agents.

Development of innovative technologies for obtaining antiparasitic drugs with a broad spectrum of action is an important problem due to the high level of danger of parasitic diseases spreading

Therefore, the development of new protivoparasitic agents remains one of the priority areas of science and technology development.

For deworming of horses in herds and wild animals in reserves by free feeding we have developed a preparation using mechano-chemical nanotechnology in the form of supramolecular complex on the basis of substance ivermectin in one stage without the participation of liquid phases using two water-soluble polymers arabinogalactan and polyvinylpyrrolidone to the formation of particles ranging in size from 0,1 (70%) to 10 microns, which is a supramolecular complex in the form of a water-soluble, tasteless powder with a readily detectable pine odor [1, 4, 5].

The aim of the study was to investigate the acute oral toxicity of supramolecular complex of ivermectin according to the Federal Law No. 61-FZ "On Circulation of Medicines" dated April 12, 2010 to determine the possible risk of animal death.

Materials and methods

The object of the study were laboratory animals kept in the vivarium of VNIIP, a branch of the K. I. Skryabin and Ya. R. Kovalenko in accordance with the rules adopted in the European Convention for the Protection of Vertebrate Animals (Strasbourg, 1986).

Preclinical studies of ivermectin complex were carried out in accordance with the Methodological Recommendations of the Pharmacological State Committee ("Guidelines for experimental (preclinical) studies of new pharmacological substances") [6].

For processing of experimental data in the study of supramolecular complex of ivermectin we used the method of Litchfield and Wilcoxon modified by Z. Roth, as it gives complete and objective information about the value of pharmacological activity of the studied drug in contrast to the method of Miller and Tainter [2].

Acute oral toxicity was studied by gastric administration of ivermectin complex and ivermectin substance for control at increased doses in white mice and rats

live weight of 18 and 160-180 g, respectively. For each dose, 10 mice and 6 rats were used. The drug was administered once with a gastric tube in doses from 40 to 350 mg/kg DV. During 14 days general clinical condition and behavior of animals, possible death, as well as manifestation of intoxication symptoms (motor activity, condition of eye membranes, consistency and color of fecal masses, feed consumption, change in body weight) were monitored. Body weight control of experimental animals was carried out before the experiment and after on the 3rd, 7th, 9th and 14th days.

Results and discussion

When the supramolecular complex of ivermectin and ivermectin substance were administered in the stomach to a group of mice (n = 10) respectively at doses of 200 and 40 mg/kg and to rats 225 and 40 mg/kg, no signs of intoxication were observed. Animals dynamically gained body weight; no pathologic-anatomical changes of internal organs were observed at slaughter and autopsy on the 14th day. When increasing the administered dose to mice and rats, the dependence of the number of dead animals on its value was established. At increased doses of supramolecular complex of ivermectin (from 250 to 400 mg/kg) and substance (from 50 to 220 mg/kg) the death of animals was noted after 1, 3, 5 and 12 days. Before death, the animals were depressed, lying buried in the bedding; shivering and brownish nasal discharge with blood were observed. At autopsy of the fallen animals, dark brown exudate with blood was observed in the lungs and abdominal cavity; the liver was enlarged, dark brown in color; dark liquid was secreted at incision; the spleen was reduced in size, black in color externally and at incision; the kidneys were enlarged, light in color, containing white dense mass at incision. The intestine contains a small amount of food masses, bloating is noted. Probably, when increased doses of drugs were administered, the animals died of hepato- and nephrotoxication, and subsequently of asphyxia. The picture of intoxication in all animals was identical.

The results of the acute oral toxicity study of the tested drugs are summarized in Tables 1 and 2.

Table 1

Results of acute oral toxicity study of supramolecular complex of ivermectin on mice and rats (n = 10)

Dose, mg/kg, by DV	Observed effect	Observed effect in %	Expected % of effect	The difference between the expected and observed effect.	X summands ²	Sum of sums, multiplied by the number of freedoms	Table of values X ² at P = 0.05	Value for confidence limits		
								S	N	/>LD _{.50}
<i>Mice</i>										
200	10/0	1,5	3,5	2	0,027	0,51	7,82	1,28	30	1,13
250	10/3	30	28	2	0,0025					
300	10/6	60	64	4	0,008					
350	10/9	90	89	1	0,0015					
400	10/10	99,2	97,5	1,7	<u>0,012</u> 0,051					
<i>Rats</i>										
225	6/0	0,3	1,0	0,7	0,005	0,2455	1,473	1,1	12	1,25
250	6/1	1,7	0,3	1,4	0,028					
275	6/2	3,3	3,0	0,3	0,0015					
300	6/3	50	60	10	0,018					
350	6/5	97,3	98,9	1,6	0,026					
400	6/6	99,7	99,0	0,7	<u>0,005</u> 0,2455					

Table 2

Results of LD (mg/kg) study of supramolecular complex of ivermectin by DV and preparation

Animal species	ld ₀ on DV/prep.	LD ₁₆ on DV/prep.	LD ₅₀ on DV/prep.	LD _M ^{no} DV/prep.	LD TM by DV/prep.
Mice	200/1000	230,0/11500	280,0/14500 (248,1 + 316,4)/ (12480 + 15640)	370,0/18500	400/20000
Rats	225/11250	260,0/13000	298,0/14598 (238,4 + 372,5)/ 11580/18572	320,0/16000	400/20000

Based on the results of acute oral toxicity study of supramolecular complex of ivermectin, the LD₅₀ for mice was found to be 280.0 (248.1 ^ 316.4) mg/kg (based on the preparation 14500 (12480 ^ 15640) mg/kg, for rats -290.0 (238.4 ^ 372.5) mg/kg, (based on the preparation 14598 (11580 ^ 18572) mg/kg).

The LD₅₀ of the ivermectin substance was 82.0 (61.2 ^ 110.1) mg/kg for mice and 165.0 (134.2 - 203.0) mg/kg for rats.

Conclusion

The picture of intoxication in mice and rats was comparable; the dependence of the number of dead individuals on the administered dose was also revealed. The toxicity of supramolecular complex of ivermectin was 3 times lower than that of ivermectin substance. Introduction of arabinogalactan into the composition of the preparation contributes to leveling of the negative effect of DV (ivermectin) in the supramolecular complex preparation on the organism of animals. The substance ivermectin has species sensitivity (mice LD₅₀ = 82.0, rats - 165.0 mg/kg).

According to the results of acute oral toxicity assessment, the LD₅₀ of the supramolecular complex of ivermectin is 280.0 for mice and 298.0 mg/kg for rats by DV and 14,500 and 14,598 mg/kg for the drug, respectively.

According to GOST 12.1.007-76, the supramolecular complex of ivermectin belongs to the 4th class of hazard [2, 3].

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